

D7.4 Update of the D&C actions

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Executive Summary

This is the deliverable 7.4 of the BIOSCHAMP project: *Update Of The D&C Actions*. The author of this document is INNOVARUM (the commercial brand of EURIZON S.L., partner 7) and Work Package 7 leader of the BIOSCHAMP project (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation).

The document summarises the communication actions carried out during the first half of the project, presenting highlights and challenges encountered. During the first half of the project, the project has focused on communication and digital actions (influenced by COVID-19 restrictions), and in total, the project has reached 7057 impacts with its actions (press release, social media, video, webpage, practice abstracts, events, media publications...).

Then, the document moves on to describe the 3 campaigns the project envisions for the next 21 months to come: *Campaign 1- Dissemination of technical results to technical audiences*, *Campaign 2 - Connecting with the mushroom industry* and *Campaign 3 - Policy recommendations*. Campaigns cover online and offline channels, specific actions, KPIs and target audiences until March 2024 (project end).

Finally, this document closes with a section dedicated to conclusions.

1 Introduction: the communication of the BIOSCHAMP project

This document is the update of the project's Dissemination and Communication Plan. The document has been prepared by INNOVARUM (the commercial brand of EURIZON S.L., partner 7) and Work Package 7 leader of the BIOSCHAMP project (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation). INNOVARUM will oversee the implementation, coordination and execution of the actions included in this document.

This document follows up on the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (CD&E Plan) - the Deliverable 7.1 of the BIOSCHAMP Project (WP7), and updates on the progress of the communication project as well as prepares and explains the steps for the next 21 months of the project.

Lastly, the final results of the communication of the project will be covered in a last WP7 document to be delivered at the end of the project in March 2024: deliverable 7.8. *Summary of the D&C actions* - Report reflecting all the D&C actions that have been undertaken in the project (due for Month 42).

These three deliverables (7.1, 7.4 and 7.8) are all open to the public.

1.1 First half of the project

The first half of the project has witnessed the deployment of the basis of the communication of the project. That is, project actions have focused on presenting the project to its audiences, its project partners, its goals, and the impact it seeks to achieve. Communication actions have also covered the progress of the different working areas of the project, participation in events and activities, participation in networks and engagement with policy audiences.

As a result, the project has progressed towards achieving the communication performance indicators established in the original CD&E Plan of the project (D7.1). It is possible to see a picture of the progress status, audience impact numbers, and the total number of actions carried out until month 21 (half of the project) in *Table 1: Progress over Communication & Dissemination - Key Performance Indicators*.

Table 1: Progress over Communication & Dissemination - Key Performance Indicators

ACTION	GROUP	TYPE	AUDIENCE	D&C LEAD	Action no. KPI	Impacts KPI	M21 KPI	M21 impacts
Final event	EVENTS	D&C*	All audiences	CTICH	1	75	0	0
Industry events	EVENTS	D	Industry	INN.	12	X	9	698
Scientific conferences	EVENTS	D	Researchers	INN.	3	X	5	140
Invitations to Policymakers	NETWORKING	D&C	Policymakers	INN. & CTICH	12	12	1	1
Networking	NETWORKING	D&C	Sustainability Networks	INN.	10	10	7	7
Flyers	PROMO MATERIALS	D&C	All audiences	INN.	1	500 prints, 100 downloads	1	76
Roll-ups	PROMO MATERIALS	D&C	All audiences	INN.	4	50 downloads ¹	1	96
Technical infographic	PROMO MATERIALS	D&C	All audiences	INN.	1	100 prints, 50 downloads	0	0
Industry magazines	PUBLICATIONS	D	Industry	INN.	4	X	3	X
Peer reviewed publications	PUBLICATIONS	D	Researchers	INN.	3	X	0	0
Practice abstracts	PUBLICATIONS	D	Researchers & Industry	CTICH	12	X	6	807
Social media LinkedIn	SOCIAL MEDIA & NEWSLETTER	C	All audiences	INN.	1	300	1	287
Social Media Twitter	SOCIAL MEDIA & NEWSLETTER	C	All audiences	INN.	1	600	1	148
Website (views/month)	WEB	C	All audiences	INN.	300	10.000 ²	402	4358
Press releases	MEDIA & PRESS RELEASES	C	All audiences	INN.	5	50 ³	1	25
Newsletter	SOCIAL MEDIA & NEWSLETTER	D&C	Industry	INN.	1	100 ⁴	1	55
Project videos	VIDEOS	C	All audiences	INN.	2	600	1	359
Project mention in partners' webs	WEB	C	All audiences	INN.	12	12	12	X
Total								7057

(1) Total downloads KPI for promo materials: 200

(2)(3)(4) KPIs established as a reference, not included in the Grant Agreement.

*D&C: Dissemination & Communication

1.1.1 Highlights

The project has impacted a total of **7,057 people** through its communication and dissemination actions up until June 2022 (month 21). Some highlights of the first half months include:

1.1.1.1 Impacts of the communication: focus on the digital channels

The launching of the **project website & the project Dissemination and Communication Plan** were the full kick-start of the project communication activities. In total, the project has attracted 4,358 web visits, 435 social media followers, 359 project presentation video views and 55 newsletter subscribers in its first 21 months. Moreover, the communication and work of the project have picked up the attention of 25 different media.

Image 1: sample of communication actions of the BIOSCHAMP project

1.1.1.2 Publications and relevant project content

The project published **6 practice abstracts** with the EIP-AGRI format: the content of the documents was prepared by CTICH (Project Coordinator) and edited by Innovarum (Communication Leader). Practice abstracts were ready in March 2022, and public dissemination started in April 2022. Up until June 2022, the 6 practice abstracts were downloaded a total of 807 times from the project webpage - a period of just 2 months. The volume of downloads has shown the relevance of the materials to the project audiences, who are interested in the project development, recommendations & results.

Image 2: BIOSCHAMP practice abstracts (2022)

1.1.1.3 High level of activity & networking despite COVID-19

Project partners have stayed active and available during the first half of the project, communicating its progress and activity despite COVID-19 limitations. In total, the project has impacted **838 people in online sectorial events**. Besides, CTICH have met with an EC Policy Officer on pesticides use (Eric Ligeois) and Innovarum promoted the connection with **7 relevant networks in sustainability and circular initiatives**.

Image 3: samples, images of BIOSCHAMP participation in industry events

1.1.2 Challenges ahead

1.1.2.1 Social media

The mushroom sector is a small niche within the social media world. For that reason, increasing reach in followers, especially on the Twitter channel has proven challenging. That said, the social media followers acquired both on Twitter & LinkedIn - as well as the newsletter subscribers - are high-quality connections: researchers or active professionals and primary producers in the mushroom industry. In other words, although the audience spectrum is limited in size, it has been proven possible to establish a relevant followers and subscribers base for the project. The second half of the project will work to increase its social media impact, overall, reaching a significant share of the EU mushroom industry.

1.1.2.2 Connections with policymakers

Establishing connections with policymakers is an effective way to promote the adoption of the innovations and recommendations prepared by the project. During the first period, Innovarum started preparing a draft list of contacts to connect with. In the new project phase to start, the project will work to further establish connections with this group. More information is available in point 2.2.6 *Networking*.

Image 4: sample of networking actions of the BIOSCHAMP project

1.1.2.3 Peer-reviewed publications

The project aims to deliver 3 peer-reviewed publications. The second half of the project will deliver the first official public results, thus, dissemination through technical, relevant publications will be a core activity of the period.

1.1.2.4 New content for the project channels

Project results will also need to be translated into different types of content and materials that address in a comprehensive manner key project content. The format of the materials will be adapted to the different project audiences: technical audiences (like in peer-reviewed publications), industry audiences, primary producers, general audiences, and policymakers.

Examples of materials to be produced include further practice abstracts, posters, technical infographics, updated webpage, newsletter & social media content and content for different mass media channels (magazines, newspapers, radio...etc.).

Image 5: sample of communication materials produced by BIOSCHAMP during the first half of the project

BIOSCHAMP proposes an integrated approach to fight against the main health challenges in mushroom production.

A biostimulant alternative casing for a sustainable and profitable mushroom industry.

- Mushroom industry productivity
- Reduce the need for pesticides
- Sustainability and profitability

12 partners **6** countries **3.5** years

@Bioschamp Bioschamp

BIOSCHAMP'S OBJECTIVES

The BIOSCHAMP project aims to develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges by:

- 1 Developing an alternative and sustainable low-peat biostimulant casing for the mushroom industry.
- 2 Reducing the dependency on and need for pesticides by 90%.
- 3 Contributing to improving the productivity, the sustainability, and the profitability of the European mushroom sector.

3 HARVEST OF MUSHROOMS

2 APPLICATION OF CASING SOIL TO INDUCE MUSHROOM FRUCTIFICATION

1 PREPARATION OF COMPOST (Substrate)

HOW DOES IT WORK?

WHO ARE THE PARTNERS?

KEY FACTS

- 12 partners
- 6 European countries
- 3.5 years

CIRCULAR ECONOMY

- Bio-based enriched and locally produced renewable material
- Low-peat alternative casing

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2 Looking ahead: the next 21 months

2.1 Goals for the next half of the project

For the second half of the project, BIOSCHAMP will:

- (1) Maintain an active communication with its audiences on the project progress through the channels opened during the first half of the project.
- (2) Focus on gathering relevant results and coordinating among project partners for proper dissemination across different channels.
- (3) Review the audiences for the activities to be developed, identifying the best segments and routes.
- (4) Assure the achievement of the Key Performance Indicators established in the Grant Agreement.

The second half of the project is expected to be intensive in results publications and research content development, relevant for the different project audiences (mushroom industries & primary producers, researchers, policymakers, & general audiences)¹. **This plan identifies a series of key results and relevant project content for communication & dissemination that is to be produced in the next 21 months; and then proposes a series of connected campaigns and actions for communication & dissemination.** The end goal of this planning is to deliver meaningful, engaging, and valuable content to the project audiences, as well as to align the next communication & dissemination actions to key moments of the project.

¹ More information on the Project audiences is available in Deliverable D7.1 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan.

Table 2: **Campaign (1)** Dissemination of technical results to technical audiences

KEY CONTENT ²	INFO AVAILABLE INTERNALLY	RELATED MILESTONE	TYPE ³	D. Audience	C. Audience	ACTIONS FOR DISSEMINATION ⁴	ACTIONS FOR COMMUNICATION	CONTENT PREPARATION
D1.1 Evaluation of alternative materials and results from small scale trials records	30/09/2022		C	Researchers	All project audiences	Technical publication (peer reviewed) - to be decided by technical partners involved	Blog post. Social media content. Other actions TBD.	WR
D2.1 Mechanisms of biostimulant action and natural chemistry involved	30/09/2022		C	Researchers	All project audiences	Technical publication (peer reviewed) - to be decided by technical partners involved	Blog post. Social media content. Other actions TBD.	UOXF
D2.2 Microbiota selection and stability results	30/09/2022	MS3-Stability of microbiota in alternative casing obtained	C	Researchers	All project audiences	Technical publication (peer reviewed) - to be decided by technical partners involved	Blog post. Social media content. Other actions TBD.	CTICH
D1.2 Physico-chemical analyses	30/09/2022		C	Researchers	All project audiences	Technical publication (peer reviewed) - to be decided by technical partners involved	Blog post. Social media content. Other actions TBD.	WR
D2.3 Tracking diagnosis development	30/09/2022		C	Researchers	All project audiences	Technical publication (peer reviewed) - to be decided by technical partners involved	Blog post. Social media content. Other actions TBD.	WR
D2.4 Report on small-scale trials: dosage optimisation evaluation	30/09/2022	MS4-Tracking tools developed	C	Researchers	All project audiences	Technical publication (peer reviewed) - to be decided by technical partners involved	Blog post. Social media content. Other actions TBD.	CTICH

² Notes on table heading titles: **D. Audience:** audiences relevant for dissemination. **C. Audiences:** audiences relevant for communication. **Date Info.** Available: date when a deliverable is submitted or when the consortium produces the content, not made available to the public. **Content preparation:** main partner in charge of the development of that content. Supported by Innovarum in content preparation.

³ Type of deliverable: **C** (confidential), **P** (public).

⁴ Communication & Dissemination actions listed in this table may be reviewed, adapted, or updated if considered necessary as the project develops.

KEY CONTENT ²	INFO AVAILABLE INTERNALLY	RELATED MILESTONE	TYPE ³	D. Audience	C. Audience	ACTIONS FOR DISSEMINATION ⁴	ACTIONS FOR COMMUNICATION	CONTENT PREPARATION
Optimised design of the BIOSCHAMP solution obtained	31/01/2023	MS6- Optimised design of the BIOSCHAMP solution obtained.	C	Researchers	All project audiences	Article in scientific magazine.	Blog post. Social media content. Press release. Newsletter.	UOXF

Table 3: **Campaign (2)** Connecting with the mushroom industry

KEY CONTENT ⁵	INFO AVAILABLE INTERNALLY	RELATED MILESTONE	TYPE ⁶	D. Audience	C. Audience	ACTIONS FOR DISSEMINATION ⁷	ACTIONS FOR COMMUNICATION	CONTENT PREPARATION
D6.1 Study on pesticides residues in compost	30/09/2023		P	Primary producers, compost industry	All project audiences	Article in scientific magazine.	Blog post. Social media content. Newsletter. Deliverable public on the web.	CTICH
D5.2 Technical documentation for end users	31/01/2024		P	Primary producers, industry	All project audiences	Technical infographic	Blog post. Social media content. Newsletter. Deliverable public on the web. Content for final event.	UOXF
D7.10 Practice abstract 2	31/01/2024		P	Primary producers, industry	All project audiences	6 Practice Abstracts - Publication in EIP Agri services	Blog post. Social media content. Newsletter. Deliverable public on the web.	CTICH
D5.3 Plan for industrialisation of alternative casing	31/03/2024	MS8 Final commercial product obtained	C	Primary producers, industry	All project audiences	TBD	Blog post. Social media content. Press release. Newsletter. Content for final event.	KBVB

⁵ Notes on table heading titles: **D. Audience:** audiences relevant for dissemination. **C. Audiences:** audiences relevant for communication. **Date Info.** Available: date when a deliverable is submitted or when the consortium produces the content, not made available to the public. **Content preparation:** main partner in charge of the development of that content. Supported by Innovarum in content preparation.

⁶ Type of deliverable: **C** (confidential), **P** (public).

⁷ Communication & Dissemination actions listed in this table may be reviewed, adapted, or updated if considered necessary as the project develops.

KEY CONTENT ⁵	INFO AVAILABLE INTERNALLY	RELATED MILESTONE	TYPE ⁶	D. Audience	C. Audience	ACTIONS FOR DISSEMINATION ⁷	ACTIONS FOR COMMUNICATION	CONTENT PREPARATION
D5.4 Plan for industrialisation of biostimulant microbiota	31/03/2024	MS8 Final commercial product obtained	C	Primary producers, industry	All project audiences	TBD	Blog post. Social media content. Newsletter. Content for final event.	FERTINAGRO
D4.1 Validation in southern European system	31/01/2024	MS7-The BIOSCHAMP solution validated in three cultivation systems	C	Primary producers, industry, policymakers	All project audiences	Industrial magazine. Poster/roll up/technical infographic	Blog post. Social media content. Press release . New poster design. Newsletter. Content for final event.	CTICH
D4.2 Validation in northern European system	31/01/2024	MS7-The BIOSCHAMP solution validated in three cultivation systems	C	Primary producers, industry, policymakers	All project audiences	Industrial magazine. Poster/roll up/technical infographic	Blog post. Social media content. New poster design. Newsletter. Content for final event.	INAGRO

Table 4: **Campaign (3)** Policy recommendations

KEY CONTENT ⁸	INFO AVAILABLE INTERNALLY	RELATED MILESTONE	TYPE ⁹	D. Audience	C. Audience	ACTIONS FOR DISSEMINATION ¹⁰	ACTIONS FOR COMMUNICATION	CONTENT PREPARATION
D6.2 Impact assessment of the use of pesticides in the EU mushroom sector	30/09/2023		P	Researchers, policymakers	All project audiences	White paper (Open Research Europe). Poster/roll up/technical infographic.	Blog post. Social media content. Newsletter. Deliverable public on the web.	CTICH
D6.4 BIOSCHAMP sustainability assessment	31/03/2024	MS9 Security and sustainability assessed	C	Researchers, policymakers	All project audiences	TBD	Blog post. Social media content. Newsletter. Content for final event.	WR

⁸ Notes on table heading titles: **D. Audience:** audiences relevant for dissemination. **C. Audiences:** audiences relevant for communication. **Date Info.** Available: date when a deliverable is submitted or when the consortium produces the content, not made available to the public. **Content preparation:** main partner in charge of the development of that content. Supported by Innovarum in content preparation.

⁹ Type of deliverable: **C** (confidential), **P** (public).

¹⁰ Communication & Dissemination actions listed in this table may be reviewed, adapted, or updated if considered necessary as the project develops.

KEY CONTENT ⁸	INFO AVAILABLE INTERNALLY	RELATED MILESTONE	TYPE ⁹	D. Audience	C. Audience	ACTIONS FOR DISSEMINATION ¹⁰	ACTIONS FOR COMMUNICATION	CONTENT PREPARATION
D6.5 Policy recommendations for mushroom biostimulants	31/03/2024		P	Researchers, policymakers	All project audiences	White paper (Open Research Europe) Technical infographic	Blog post. Social media content. Press release. Newsletter. Deliverable public on the web. Content for final event.	CTICH

2.2 Coordination of dissemination & communication actions

Innovarum, as Dissemination & Communication Leader, will coordinate the implementation of the actions listed, with special support from the “Content production” partners identified in the list. That said, all partners will continue taking part in the communication of the project, supporting more actively, or contributing to specific actions if requested.

2.2.1 Technical peer reviewed publications

Innovarum will launch a **coordination meeting with all technical partners in September 2022**, to bring up the relevant identified topics for publication & relevant journals identified (*Table 3: peer-reviewed journals examples to be proposed to technical partners*) and coordinate a working calendar for publications. Technical partners (WR, UOXF, etc.) will be responsible for the production, validation, and publication of the content.¹¹

Table 5: peer-reviewed journal examples to be proposed to technical partners

Peer-reviewed journals	Link	Author Guidelines
Frontiers in Microbiology	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology	https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology#author-guidelines
Science of The Total Environment	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/science-of-the-total-environment	https://www.elsevier.com/journals/science-of-the-total-environment/0048-9697/guide-for-authors
Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry	https://pubs.acs.org/journal/jafcau	https://pubs.acs.org/page/jafcau/submission/reference-guidelines.html
PloS One	https://journals.plos.org/plosone/	https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/submission-guidelines
Chemosphere	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/chemosphere	https://www.elsevier.com/journals/chemosphere/0045-6535/guide-for-authors
Fungal Biology	https://www.journals.elsevier.com/fungal-biology	https://www.elsevier.com/journals/fungal-biology/1878-6146/guide-for-authors
Applied and Environmental Microbiology	https://aem.asm.org/	https://aem.asm.org/sites/default/files/additional-assets/AEM-ITA.pdf

2.2.1.1 Update on the coordination meeting to identify topics for publication and relevant journals

During the online Executive Board meeting on the 22nd of June 2022, the consortium discussed relevant journals for peer-reviewed publications, including those listed in *Table 4: peer-reviewed journal examples to be proposed to technical partners*, and their links to BIOSCHAMP’s WPs. The consortium also defined a list of potential candidates for publishing peer-reviewed publications: WR (WP1); UOXF, CSIC and CTICH (WP2); INAGRO and CTICH (WP3); and WR (WP6). It was also decided to hold a coordination meeting in September 2022 to review which results could be published as peer-reviewed articles during RP2.

Finally, the discussion took place during BIOSCHAMP’s 2nd General Assembly (GA), physically held in Belgium on 30th of November and 1st of December 2022. During a careful revision of the status of the project, it was determined that results were not suitable for publication, due to their low success rate. Thus, the monitoring

¹¹ Partners involved in the publication and dissemination of results will respect the Grant Agreement notifications period to the consortium, to avoid any confidentiality breakage or conflict of interests.

of publishable results was performed with special meticulousity during 2023 through individual WP meetings and periodic Innovation Team meetings. has also worked to deliver the first peer reviewed publication of the project: A publication leaded by UNIPG and related to the Bioschamp LCA “Assessing the variability in environmental impacts of Agaricus bisporus ((J.E.Lange) Imbach) mushroom production systems across Europe”, has been submitted for publication but is still under review. Two more publications – manuscripts are in writing: One describing the characterisation of the biobank and the identification of *B. velezensis* strains with biocontrol activity against mycoparasites leaded by UOXF and another one based on our experiences of developing transformation approaches for *B. velezensis* leaded by WR. The outcome of these processes will be reported in D7.8. *Summary of the D&C actions.*

2.2.2 Sectorial magazines and general publications

Innovarum will also encourage all project partners to connect with relevant local and national sectorial magazines. Furthermore, connected to key moments of project progress (as identified in *Table 2: key milestones and content to be produced by BIOSCHAMP until March 2024 & key D&C actions addressed to them*), Innovarum will coordinate with partners to produce an article covering the event, for example on topics and moments such as¹²:

1. January 2023: MS6- Optimised design of the BIOSCHAMP solution obtained.
2. September 2023: D6.1 Study on pesticides residues in compost.
3. January 2024: MS7-The BIOSCHAMP solution validated in three cultivation systems.

Some examples of relevant magazines are included in *Table 5: industry magazines examples.*

Table 6: industry magazines examples

Industry magazines	Link	Contact (editor)
Mushroom Business	https://www.mushroombusiness.com/	roel@mushroombusiness.com
Fungimag	https://fungimag.com/	fungimag@gmail.com
The International Society for Mushroom Science	http://www.isms.biz/articles/	
Mushroom news	https://www.americanmushroom.org/main/mushroom-news/	info@americanmushroom.org

2.2.3 Key moments for social media campaigns, media coverage & press releases

Identified key dates for **social media communications** regarding project progress (including webpage, newsletter, blog content writing...etc) cover:

1. January 2023: MS6- Optimised design of the BIOSCHAMP solution obtained.
2. September 2023: D6.2 Impact assessment of the use of pesticides in the EU mushroom sector.
3. January 2024: MS7-The BIOSCHAMP solution validated in three cultivation systems, D7.10 Practice abstract 2.
4. and March 2024: MS8 Final commercial product obtained, D6.5 Policy recommendations for mushroom biostimulants, project end.

These four moments will be aligned together with **press releases** and special mentions in the **website blog**, looking to further call the **attention of the media** at national and EU level.

2.2.4 Events

Innovarum will also oversee the participation of project partners in different key broad **sectorial events at EU level & scientific conferences; encouraging & supporting the consortium to participate in events at local and national levels.**

Event dates follow specific calendars according to the organising bodies; thus, it was not possible to include them in *Table 2: key milestones and content to be produced by BIOSCHAMP until March 2024 & key D&C actions addressed to them.* To make the most of events, Innovarum will keep active communication channels with the project partners to showcase the results available of the BIOSCHAMP project in events when opportunities arise.

Besides, Innovarum will also periodically review and inform partners of new sectorial events dates. For now, coming relevant events where BIOSCHAMP is planning to participate include:

Table 7: relevant events for BIOSCHAMP 2021-2023

Industry event	Link	Partner	Date	Location	Content to present
The 11 th International Medicinal Mushroom Conference	https://www.immc11.com/	EKOFUNGI	27/09/2022	Online	General presentation of the project. Techniques for microbiota isolation.
IFIB 2022	https://ifibwebsite.com/posters-session-call-for-abstracts/	CTICH/INN.	29/09/2022	Virtual poster session + onsite in Bari (Italy)	Alternative materials to replace peat in mushroom industry
Congreso de la Sociedad Española de Fitopatología	https://vlcsef2022.com/	CTICH	24-26/10/2022	Valencia, Spain	Suppressive effect of biostimulants against pathogens
EFIB 2022	https://efibforum.com/	TBD	26/10/2022	Vilnius, Lithuania	TBD
EU Green Week 2023	TBD	TBD	May-June 2023	TBD	TBD
Mushroom Days 2023	https://www.champignondagen.nl/en/welcome/	All	2023 – TBC ¹³	Netherlands	Project presentation. Interim results of the project.
Fieragricola 2024	https://www.fieragricola.it/it	TBD	31/01/2024	Verona, Italy	TBD

2.2.5 Promo materials, practice abstracts & videos

Innovarum will produce new **technical infographics** to summarise visually the research, innovations and results of the project. Additionally, it will also produce **3 new posters** (or roll-ups, to be decided) to showcase the project results in visual events. Materials will be distributed among partners and printed for onsite events.

¹³ TBC: To Be Confirmed

Topics for future materials include:

1. September 2023: graphic material on the impact assessment of the use of pesticides in the EU mushroom sector.
2. January 2024: visual material on the technical specifications about the final BIOSCHAMP product for product use by mushroom growers.
3. January 2024: A technical visual scheme: the BIOSCHAMP solution validated in three cultivation systems.

BIOSCHAMP will also produce **6 new practice abstracts (EIP-Agri format)** in January 2024. This new batch of practice abstracts, as well as the 6 previous practice abstracts published (12 in total), will be translated into the languages of the project partners to increase impact and outreach.

Additionally, Innovarum will coordinate the recording of a **second project video** – potential date for the recording of the video is November 2022, together with the next project General Assembly.

2.2.6 Networking

Innovarum will oversee the networking activities with the support of the consortium, especially from the Project Coordinator (CTICH). The goal will be to establish further connections and impactful activities with **sustainability networks**, such as, for example, the EU Green Week 2022 event.

Additionally, Innovarum will oversee the development of contacts with **policymakers**. Key moments for connection and impact to this audience group include:

1. September 2023: production of the impact assessment of the use of pesticides in the EU mushroom sector.
2. January 2024, with the validation of the BIOSCHAMP solution in three cultivation systems.
3. March 2024, with the set of policy recommendations for mushroom biostimulants.

To connect with policymakers, Innovarum (as Communication leader) will:

1. Develop a list of policy contacts at regional, national and EU levels. This work already started during the first 21 months of the project.
2. Establish initial connections through general project materials, presentations, and meetings.
3. As September 2023 approaches, oversee the publication of a series of white papers, to be concluded in March 2024 with the final “Policy recommendations for mushroom biostimulants”. These white papers are to be published in open data platforms as *Open Research Europe*¹⁴, and sent to the policy contacts previously identified.

2.2.7 Final event

The final event will be organised in Spain, La Rioja by CTICH (Project Coordinator) in September-October 2024. BIOSCHAMP will invite key stakeholders from the audiences of the project, reaching a minimum of 75 participants.

The final event will be a key moment to present the final policy recommendations (biostimulants/pesticide use), the peer-reviewed publications available and the next steps of the project in regard to industrial development and market uptake.

¹⁴ Link: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

2.3 How to produce and validate content?

To generate **public, engaging and newsworthy content** for the project audiences for the all the communications formats above, Innovarum will request all partners a **500 non-confidential summary of all confidential deliverables** they produce. Additionally, Innovarum will also **review public deliverables** and maintain an active communication with all project partners, making sure information and updates are disseminated properly.

This way, the project will count with authorised, fully public updates on the project progress to comment, talk, share, and produce content in different formats (web, newsletter, promo materials, etc.).

2.4 Exploitation Plan

Considering the input received during the review meeting held on 15th June 2022, it was decided to launch an Innovation Team focused on debating the commercialisation of the BIOSCHAMP solution, establishing a supply chain, discussing implementation activities and following up the Exploitation Plan. During the 2nd GA of the project (held onsite in Belgium), the consortium agreed on the composition (CTICH, WR, INAGRO, INNV, NEWFOSS and KBVB) and launch date of the Innovation Team (January 2023).

The Innovation Team met three times during 2023. Discussions included the results of the project's alternative casing soils and biostimulants, and their suitability for commercialisation. It was determined that results on biostimulants were not auspicious enough to analyse their commercialisation and supply chain. On the other hand, these characteristics were to be determined for alternative casing soils, due to the promising character of their results.

Regarding the patent "*Bacteria strains (B. velezensis CM5, B. velezensis CM19, B. velezensis CM35 and variants thereof) and methods for controlling the growth of crop pathogenic microorganisms and improving crop growth*" covered under UK patent application number GB202009235A (filed on 17th June 2020 by Oxford University Innovation Ltd. (OUI)). OUI had decided not to commercially exploit the invention. CTICH as project coordinator decided to take over the patent and continue the process by filing the application in the European Patent Office (application number EP21734105A). The resolution of this application is still underway.

Given the focus of the Innovation Team on technical advances and the definition of contingency plans, it was decided to create a **Commercialisation Team** focused on the commercialisation structure and further exploitation of the BIOSCHAMP solution. The Commercialisation Team is led by KBVB and includes CTICH, WR, NEWFOSS and INNOVARUM. It is expected to have the final results on commercialisation structure and market availability for the BIOSCHAMP solution by early June 2024 (M45). This information will be included in D7.5 *Commercialisation strategy* (due September 2024, M8).

3 Conclusions

The BIOSCHAMP project has worked the first twenty-one months of the project to generate awareness among its target audiences about the project goals, objectives and partners involved. To do this, it has used videos, communication materials, media publications, social media posts, events... Besides, it has also worked to disseminate the first results and relevant content for dissemination produced by the project in the shape of practice abstracts (EIP-Agri format). As a result, from October 2020 to June 2021 the project has impacted **7,057 people**.

For the next half of the project, BIOSCHAMP will focus on results dissemination, as well as on the challenges identified during the first half of the project: social media channels growth, content production, development of peer-reviewed publications and relevant connections with policymakers. For that purpose, BIOSCHAMP has structured 3 campaigns that will cover key project results to come and work towards the final achievement of the KPIs of the project. The campaigns combine online and offline actions through different channels:

1. Campaign 1 - Dissemination of technical results to technical audiences
2. Campaign 2 - Connecting with the mushroom industry
3. Campaign 3 - Policy recommendations

BIOSCHAMP has also determined results from WP1, WP2 and WP6 are suitable for peer-reviewed publications. Preparation, review, and publication of said articles will take place during 2023 and 2024, contributing to the dissemination and communication of the project.

Regarding exploitation, BIOSCHAMP has established two working groups:

1. An Innovation Team, that has assessed the technical advances on alternative casing soils and biostimulants, determined strategies to overcome their shortcomings, and decided that the status of biostimulants is not advanced enough to undertake the planning of their commercialisation.
2. A Commercialisation Team, that will address the commercialisation structure and possible exploitation of the BIOSCHAMP solution.

During the second half of the project, the exploitation of BIOSCHAMP will also be marked by the resolution of a patent application at the European Patent Office.

The results of the project will be summarised and presented at BIOSCHAMP's final event, to be held the final month of the project at La Rioja (Spain).